

EL PRESIDENTE DEL COMITÉ DE ÉTICA PARA LA INVESTIGACIÓN CIENTÍFICA

CERTIFICA:

Que el proyecto titulado "EFECTO NUTRICIONAL DE LA PROTEÍNA HIDROLIZADA DE VÍSCERAS DE TRUCHA CONCENTRADA POR SEPARACIÓN MECÁNICA EN DIETAS EXTRUIDAS PARA TILAPIA ROJA (*Oreochromis spp*)" presentado por el Doctor **José Luis Hoyos Concha**, adscrito a la Facultad de Ciencias Agrarias, cumple con los requerimientos ético legales.

Por tanto, el Comité de Ética para la Investigación Científica de la Universidad del Cauca, avala el proyecto según acta N° 6.1 - 1.25/15 del día 05 de agosto de 2019.

La presente se expide a solicitud de la parte interesada.

Se firma en Popayán, a los cinco (05) días del mes de agosto de dos mil diecinueve (2019).

FRANKLYN FAJARDO SANDOVAL

Presidente Comité de Ética para la Investigación Científica

ISO 9001: SC-CER450832

IQNet: CO- SC-CER450832

Hacia una Universidad comprometida con la paz territorial

Vicerrectoría de Investigaciones
Carrera 2 No. 1A – 25 Popayán Cauca- Colombia
Teléfono: Conmutador 8209800 Exts. 2630
vri@unicauca.edu.co www.unicauca.edu.co

El Director del Grupo de Investigación ASUBAGROIN

Hace constar

Que: el artículo **“Effect of hydrolyzed red worm (*Eisenia foétida*) on production parameters in red tilapia (*Oreochromis sp.*)”** es parte del Proyecto **“EFECTO NUTRICIONAL DE LA PROTEÍNA HIDROLIZADA DE VÍSCERAS DE TRUCHA CONCENTRADA POR SEPARACIÓN MECÁNICA EN DIETAS EXTRUIDAS PARA TILAPIA ROJA (*Oreochromis sp.*)**, el cual cuenta con el aval del comité de ética de la Universidad del Cauca según acta No. 6.1-1.25/15 del día 05 de Agosto de 2019 (Anexo).

En tal sentido, la publicación propuesta a la revista titulada **“F1000Research”** es producto del proyecto mencionado y demás que deriven de este. Por ende se cumple con el requisito del aval de ética para el uso de animales en investigación.

La presente se expide a solicitud de la parte interesada.

Se firma en Popayán, a los 16 días del mes de Agosto de dos mil veinticuatro (2024)

JOSE LUIS HOYOS CONCHA
Director
Grupo de Investigación ASUBAGROIN

Animal Welfare Protocol in the study “Effect of hydrolyzed red worm (*Eisenia foétida*) on production parameters in red tilapia (*Oreochromis sp.*)”

Introduction:

The present study was carried out under strict animal welfare protocols, following the ICA recommendations in its Methodology guide for the evaluation of animal welfare in aquatic animals (farmed fish for human consumption). Minimizing the stress and suffering of the fish was prioritized at all times.

The welfare of experimental animals is a priority in our research. For this reason, measures were implemented to ensure that the fish used in this study had a high quality of life.

Methods:

Obtaining the fish: The fish were supplied by the fish farming station belonging to the Jaime Isaza Cadavid Colombian Polytechnic University. They were transported and acclimatized to the laboratory conditions for 15 days before the start of the experimental phase.

Maintenance conditions: Maintenance conditions: The fish were kept in 75-liter aquariums with a continuous filtration and aeration system, they were guaranteed an ideal area to reduce stress due to confinement. The water temperature was kept constant at 26 °C and the photoperiod was 12 hours of daylight.

Feeding: Before the start of the experimental phase, the fish were fed with the experimental diets for 10 days in order to adapt the digestive system to the type of food to be tested. The diets were prepared according to the requirements for the species and thus guarantee optimal physical condition. During the study phase, the evaluation diets were supplied until "apparent satiety" three times a day (8:00 a.m., 12:00 p.m. and 4:00 p.m.), the food was offered according to the biomass of the animals. Additionally, uneaten food and feces were removed daily in the morning (9:00 a.m.) and in the afternoon (5:00 p.m.) by siphoning and 60% water changes were performed in the aquariums, physicochemical parameters were measured to avoid alterations in water quality and minimize stress on the fish.

Experimental design: 90 fish (10 per aquarium) were randomly distributed in 9 aquariums, evaluating 3 treatments with 3 replicates each. Periodic evaluations of the health status of the fish were carried out, including parameters to be evaluated, body size and weight, body condition, and behavior.

At the end of the experiment, the fish were returned to the ponds of the fish farming station so that they could continue their production cycle according to the farm's ethical recommendations.

Results:

During the experiment, no signs of stress, illness or injury were observed in the fish.

The fish maintained adequate growth and healthy body condition throughout the experiment.

Discussion:

"The results obtained in this study demonstrate that it is possible to evaluate the effect of different diets on the growth and health of fish without compromising their well-being."

The implementation of rigorous animal welfare protocols is essential to ensure the scientific validity of studies in fish.

Conclusion:

The fish were kept in optimal conditions to ensure their well-being throughout the experiment. A continuous filtration and aeration system was implemented to ensure good water quality. Feeding was done three times a day to avoid overfeeding and starvation. At the end of the experiment, the fish were reintegrated into the production system.

Additional Considerations:

Local regulations: It complied with the regulations issued by the ICA related to animal welfare in research.

Welfare evaluation: objective and subjective indicators were used to evaluate the well-being of the fish, such as physiological and behavioral parameters.

The Ethics Committee for Scientific Research of the University of Cauca, endorses the project according to minutes No. 6.1 - 1.25/15 of August 5, 2019.